

Metro-Haul

METRO High bandwidth, 5G Application-aware optical network, with edge storage, compute and low latency

Grant No. 761727

Deliverable D5.1

Report on vertical use cases performance metrics

Abstract

This deliverable describes the performance metrics of the demonstrator work to be done in WP5, and it elaborates upon the ten vertical use cases defined by WP2. Each use case is first discussed and analysed in terms of feasibility of experimental validation, innovation to be demonstrated, and possible portability aspects. Such analysis has been used to drive the selection of the vertical use cases that will be validated by WP5. The following three demos were identified: (1) Crowdsourced video broadcasts; (2) Real-time low-latency object tracking; and (3) Portable Demo on Media and Entertainment.

This document then provides the KPIs to meet the requirements of the three selected demos, providing feedback and inputs for specific data and control plane technical solutions to be designed and validated within the Metro-Haul project.

Document properties

Status and Version:		
Date of issue:	08/03/2018	
Distribution:	Public	
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Revision History

Revision	Date	Responsible	Comment
0.0	09/01/2018	Editor	Initial version
0.1 - 0.2	25/01/2018	All	All partners providing contributions to Chapter 2 and 3
0.3	05/02/2018	Editor	Added abstract, ex. summary, introduction
0.4-0.5	12-19/02/2018	All	All partners finalizing contributions
0.6-0.8	20-28/02/2018	Editor	Reviewed by A. Rafael, M. Parker
0.9	07/03/2018	All	Final updates upon review
0.91	09/03/2018	Reviewer	Reviewed by M. Parker
0.92	10/03/2018	Editor, Reviewers	Final version
1.0	12/03/2018	Editor, Reviewers	Final editorial work

Executive Summary

The Metro-Haul solution being designed as the project progresses, is expected to successfully address the future 5G service requirements via a new generation of optical metro nodes featuring full compute and storage capabilities, and be capable of effectively interfacing both 5G access and multi-Tbit/s elastic core networks.

The design of the new Metro-Haul network architecture is being undertaken in WP2, where a number of use cases have been analysed (see D2.1), and from which the Metro-Haul general requirements and KPIs have also been defined. The Metro-Haul KPIs have been designed to be closely aligned to the 5G-PPP KPIs, but to additionally reflect the metro-centric perspective and objectives of the project. In WP5, these outputs from WP2 are now being further elaborated and their feasibilities evaluated with a view to specifically selecting a subset of them for the project vertical use case validations and demonstrations. In addition, it is expected that the selected vertical use cases will particularly demonstrate the functionality advantages, cost benefits, and operational efficiencies that are anticipated to be specifically enabled by the Metro-Haul architecture solution.

This document aims to define the Metro-Haul KPIs that meet the requirements of the service use cases and that can be measured in the demos. The Metro-Haul KPIs were already identified during project preparation: the most relevant service KPIs identified by 5GPPP were translated into the following Metro-Haul network KPIs and specifications:

- MH1: 100 x more 5G capacity supported over the same optical fibre infrastructure (edge processing)
- MH2: 10 times less energy consumption
- MH3: Latency-aware metro network in which latency-sensitive slices are handled at the metro edge ensuring the metro network adds no additional latency.
- MH4: End-to-end SDN-based management framework enabling fast configuration time to set up, or to reconfigure services handling 5G applications, specifically 1 minute for simple network path set-up, 10 minutes for full installation of a new VNF, and 1 hour for setting up a new virtual network.
- MH5: Reduction in CAPEX of a factor of 10, plus a reduction in OPEX of at least 20%.

Among the aforementioned Metro-Haul KPIs, MH1, MH3 and MH4 are the most suitable ones for validation in comprehensive experimental demonstrations, and are specifically targeted by WP5. Indeed, the validation of MH2 requires specific technological studies that are already in place in WP3 to achieve 10 times less energy consumption (e.g., design and assessment of photonic integrated components). Similarly, the validation of MH5 for CAPEX and OPEX reduction requires studies and techno-economic analysis that are ongoing in WP2. To avoid repetitions, in this document, we therefore mainly focus on MH1, MH3 and MH4.

In this document, the ten use cases identified by WP2 (see D2.1) are first discussed for possible demo validation. Specific focus is devoted to two vertical use cases that will be validated at the end of the project in the field trials located in Berlin and in the UK, respectively. Moreover, this document discusses the feasibility of implementing additional demos to show the performance of the Metro-Haul network, including a portable demo to be showcased in relevant public events. This document also provides inputs into the project to define specific technical solutions and strategies compliant to the fulfilment of the requirements, as well as to guarantee the validation of the considered objectives.

More specifically, the following ten use cases proposed by WP2 (see D2.1) are here considered and further elaborated:

a) mIoT Utility metering

Utility metering applications will be able to rely on the Metro-Haul network to support packet pre-processing in network resources, including aggregation, sanity checking, and even error correction. Thanks to these features, mIoT traffic will be reduced and optimized, while the QoE of its users will be enhanced by reduced response times, and early control and detection of failures. Nevertheless, the utility metering scenario is complex and requires many users connected to AMEN nodes, which together with the lack of standardized commercial solutions make this scenario less suitable for demonstration as compared to the others proposed.

b) Capacity planning of Content Delivery Networking

The Metro-Haul solution for effective capacity planning of CDNs relies on storage/caching capabilities placed at the AMENs and/or MCEN. The use of these resources, at the expense of their deployment cost, allows the improvement of customers' QoE, by reducing the latency and jitter of video delivery, and simultaneously optimizes the bandwidth required for CDN services over the metro network. The Metro-Haul solution for capacity planning of CDN, being a techno-economic design study, is not suitable for demo validation. However, as discussed in the next point, in WP5, the overall CDN use case can be demonstrated on the aspects of control, orchestration, and management.

c) Live-TV distribution

Live-TV distribution imposes stringent requirements on metro networks, in terms not only of bandwidth and QoS (including jitter and packet loss), but also in terms of number of flows for the end-users to be managed, and the need of computation at the edges of the metro networks to reduce the amount of traffic to be conveyed. In this use case, the support of Metro-Haul for CDNs in general and Live-TV in particular can be demonstrated, also from the perspective of the control, orchestration, and management (CMO).

d) Service Robotics

A potential integration of lab experiments using flying drones and Metro-Haul network infrastructure is under evaluation at the TIM Innovation Labs. Such a trial will leverage the computing resources hosted on CORD nodes of the FutureNet TIM test bed for the dynamic allocation and execution of part of the Service Robotics functionality; specifically the drone controller that is an element requiring stringent constraints in terms of latency and data rate.

e) Smart Factory

This use case represents the introduction of Internet and IoT technologies within the manufacturing processes. The implementation of the Smart Factory enables the centralisation of many tasks, like video surveillance, and remote robot control, etc. The feasibility of demonstrating this use case would be limited to show high availability by using the SDN/Controller to quickly restore connectivity over the Metro-Haul architecture after a fault.

f) 6DoF Virtual Reality

This use case corresponds to next-generation VR (Virtual Reality), and encompasses both AR (Augmented Reality) and MR (Mixed Reality) experiences. Among all the possible service implementations, we are looking at an immersive experience that allows the end user at home to virtually move within a remote live event (for instance within a stadium during a football match) by using a 5G mobile connected VR Head Mounted Device. This use case requires a very high bandwidth through the optical metro, as well as high computing power

at both the AMEN and MCEN nodes. The multicast capabilities of the optical nodes being developed in WP3, along with their open interfaces with the SDN controller, opens the opportunity to demonstrate how the optical metro network can be reconfigured in order to minimise the total capacity needed in the network when new service requests arrive at the service controller, by using the multicast functionality of the optical nodes.

g) Intelligent environments to support Autonomous Driving

Autonomous driving is currently under development and expected to be generalized by 2025. This new paradigm for driving opens new possibilities regarding not only the autonomous vehicles themselves, but also the traffic environments, from which Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) can obtain useful knowledge regarding the agents within their surroundings and other situations. Metro-Haul network capabilities would support the provision of extremely low latency networks to enable fast communication between AVs, servers, and other driving agents.

h) Enterprise Access with NG Ethernet

Metro-Haul will provide standard NG Ethernet interfaces working at 100 Gb/s, which, along with an end-to-end controller, can be used by enterprises for critical applications such as data replication, lowering its cost with respect to using dark fibre products. Thus, it is very important to guarantee that the network is providing the KPIs that are being contracted, so that the deployment of probes that are able to measure connection bandwidths, latency, and packet loss is therefore also necessary.

i) Crowdsourced video broadcasts

Crowdsourced video streaming is a paradigm shift in how video content is generated and shared across scalable networks. The success of the service depends on synchronizing user-generated video streams and capturing them in the cloud, requiring a high capacity network which adapts and scales dynamically. This use case was pre-selected to be shown (in the UK) at the end of the project, and will show the use of Metro-Haul network and orchestrator capabilities to construct a scalable crowdsourced video service. It will showcase the solution's ability to support high capacity, dynamic crowdsourced video streaming applications at the AMEN & MCEN aimed for public events.

j) Real-time low-latency object tracking

In a future smart city scenario with a foreseeable high density of fixed and mobile CCTV cameras, the project will build a demonstrator (in Berlin) showing an integrated solution for real-time low-latency object tracking with complete handover between various video cameras. Real-time identification for security purposes and tracking functions (algorithms), requiring low-latency processing and transmission, can be flexibly and automatically distributed for edge computing inside AMENs using a CORD (Central Office Re-architected as a Datacenter) setup. Service function chaining for system-wide control will be provided using a combination of SDN and NFV technologies.

A subset of these vertical use cases has been selected for actual demo validation, with the following three demos being identified:

- 1. Crowdsourced video broadcasts**
- 2. Real-time low-latency object tracking**
- 3. Portable Demo on Media and Entertainment**

The first two demos, related to the vertical use cases (i) and (j) respectively, were pre-selected in the Metro-Haul project proposal phase since they can validate, in a complementary way, the aforementioned relevant Metro-Haul KPIs.

The third demo, related to vertical use cases in the broad area of media and entertainment, has been selected for demonstration since it is portable (i.e., enabling the showcase to be demonstrated at relevant events in different locations) and it encompasses requirements, technologies, and solutions that are common for multiple use cases analysed in WP2. For example, it can validate the software components in support of: (b) the CDN use case, (c) the Live TV use case, and (f) the 6DoF use case. Moreover, it is suitable for the integration and experimentation of the passive and active network measurement probes listed in (h). This vertical use case will also allow us to further validate a relevant set of specific KPIs included in the KPI MH4 on “End-to-end SDN-based management framework enabling fast configuration time to set up or reconfigure services handling 5G applications”.

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1. Introduction

The Metro-Haul project objectives are closely aligned to KPIs emerging from 5GPPP, with the main 5GPPP KPIs addressed in this project being:

- 5GPPP1 – 1000 times higher mobile data volume per geographical area.
- 5GPPP2 – 10 times to 100 times higher typical user data rate.
- 5GPPP3 – 10 times lower energy consumption.
- 5GPPP4 – End-to-End latency of < 1-10 ms
- 5GPPP5 – Scalable management framework enabling fast deployment of novel applications
- 5GPPP6 – Reduction of the network management OPEX by at least 20% compared to today.

As reported in the DoW and D2.1, these *service* KPIs have been converted into *network* KPIs and specifications of direct relevance to Metro-Haul:

- MH1 – 100 x more 5G capacity supported over the same optical fibre infrastructure. This embraces 5GPPP1 and 5GPPP2.
- MH2 – 10 times less energy consumption. This mirrors 5GPPP3 above and again compares the Metro-Haul solution to existing solutions that would support the same 5G services.
- MH3 – Latency-aware metro network in which latency-sensitive slices are handled at the metro edge ensuring the metro network adds no additional latency. This deals with 5GPPP4 – minimizing the delays over the metro network for applications requiring this. By differentiating applications according to their latency requirements and monitoring the Metro-Haul performance in real time, edge resources will not be wasted on applications that don't need them.
- MH4 – End-to-end SDN-based management framework enabling fast configuration time to set up or reconfigure services handling 5G applications, specifically 1 minute for simple network path set-up and 10 minutes for full installation of a new VNF, and 1 hour for setting up a new virtual network slice. This reflects 5GPPP5.
- MH5 – Reduction in CAPEX of a factor of 10, plus a reduction in OPEX of at least 20%. This reflects 5GPPP6 but also adds an additional Metro-Haul CAPEX requirement. Although this seems ambitious at first sight, it should be considered as the cost to provide a metro network capable of delivering the same 5G KPIs to today's solutions. Cost reductions will be seen in the following areas:
 - Development of cost-effective components
 - More efficient use of metro transport resources
 - Whitebox / buying direct applied to Ethernet switches, optical switches and transponders
 - Edge processing, reducing traffic load on the metro network
 - Dynamic application scheduling, eliminating equipment over provisioning

These five general targets, together with the additional requirements coming from different and complementary lines of analysis detailed by WP2 in D2.1, are being considered by WP5.

This D5.1 deliverable aims to deliver, according to the aforementioned KPIs, the set of specific requirements, specifications and KPIs for the Metro-Haul solutions that will be validated and demonstrated including Vertical Industries.

Such KPIs will constitute the feedback to WP3 and WP4, for the design and implementation of the related hardware and software technologies and solutions. Moreover, they will be the reference for future WP5 activities on the experimental validation of the overall Metro-Haul architecture, the

testing of the developed systems including interactions between all Metro-Haul components and on the design and implementation of demonstrations to be showcased at relevant events (e.g., involving the control plane and agent control Interfaces) in various locations.

In this document, all the use cases identified by WP2 are first considered and discussed in terms of demonstration potentials. More specifically, Chapter 2 dedicates a subsection to each of the ten vertical use cases defined by WP2, whereby in each subsection, a brief description of the related vertical use case is reported as derived from D2.1. Another subsection then analyses each vertical use case and discusses the validation feasibility and innovation to be demonstrated in each case. Finally, each vertical use case is also discussed in terms of its *portability*, i.e. aiming at identifying the most suitable portable use case to be showcased in relevant public events at various locations.

In Chapter 3, three demos are identified to show the benefits of the Metro-Haul solution when applied to implement some specific vertical use cases. In particular, these three demos will be implemented by WP5 and considered for the validation of all the Metro-Haul objectives and solutions over the relevant selection of the aforementioned ten vertical use cases. For these particular vertical use cases that have been considered, the specific aspects to be demonstrated are discussed in greater detail, including the targeted KPIs to be demonstrated. Finally, a high-level scheduling and preliminary discussion on the relevant feedback/requirements into WP3 and WP4 are also discussed.

2. Analysis of Vertical Use Cases defined by WP2 from WP5 perspective

This chapter discusses from the WP5 perspective the vertical use cases as defined in WP2. In particular, the ten Metro-Haul use cases reported in D2.1 and summarized in Table 1 are here reconsidered. After a brief summary, each use case is discussed in terms of its feasibility, highlighting the technical aspects and related innovation to be potentially demonstrated within Metro-Haul.

Table 1 – List of WP2 service use cases (see D2.1)

No	Use case name	Service Class	Vertical	Coverage extension
1	mIoT Utility metering	mIoT	Utilities	Smart City
2	Content Delivery Network	eMBB	Media & Ent.	Everywhere
3	Live TV distribution	eMBB + URLLC	Media & Ent.	Everywhere
4	Service Robotics	eMBB + URLLC	Cloud Services	Smart City
5	Smart Factory	URLLC + eMBB + mIoT	Industry 4.0	Industrial Plant
6	6DoF Virtual Reality	eMBB + URLLC	Media & Ent.	Indoor hotspot
7	Intelligent Transport System and Autonomous Driving	eMBB + URLLC	Automotive	Roads
8	Enterprise Access with NG Ethernet	BB + URLLC	Cloud Services	Everywhere (not rely on mobile access)
9	Crowdsourced video broadcasts	URLLC	Media & Ent.	Crowd location
10	Real-time low-latency object tracking	URLLC	Pub. Saf. & Env.	Smart City

2.2 mIoT Utility metering

2.2.3 Brief description

mIoT utility metering is a Metro-Haul scenario where sensor measurements (such as water or gas consumption) are collected and sent to a central server in the cloud for analysis and subsequent decision-making. The problem with this kind of traffic is that it entails a constant flow of small packets distributed through the access network that incurs a very large overhead when sent separately to the central office.

In such an application scenario, Metro-Haul offers pre-processing, aggregation, and early detection capabilities at AMEN nodes, so considerably reducing the number of packets to be delivered into the metro-core network, as well as avoiding other overheads thanks to early detection and sanity-checking of metering, leading if required to retaking measurements from the AMEN node.

The Metro-Haul network requirements for this application rely heavily on the Metro-Haul paradigm of bringing computing power into the network at the AMEN nodes, and through NFV to supply mIoT service providers with the resources to aggregate, simplify, and ensure the validity of measurements prior to delivering them to the central servers.

2.2.4 Feasibility

In the Metro-Haul setup, different applications could leverage the in-node computing to aggregate, combine and even reduce the effective traffic offered to the metro network, by providing cached or predefined responses to simple user requests, combining requests to be sent to central servers, or requiring more information prior to delivery. The mIoT utility metering case is therefore an example

application for such capabilities, where the traffic generated by measurements comprising many very small packets can be condensed into a single packet.

In fact, mIoT utility metering scenarios are fairly complex, as they require large access networks comprising multiple households sending small packets very frequently. Despite this setup existing in many metro networks, which could potentially be utilized for demonstration purposes, there are currently no standards in utility metering applications, nor do current solutions enjoy sufficiently widespread deployment, which suggests that the other scenarios contained in this report are more suitable to showing the achievements and improvements of the Metro-Haul network.

Thus the availability of these kind of sensors is currently scarce and very limited, being expensive and still in the early stages of development, with the measurements not standardized with a consequent lack of interoperability and homogeneity of the records. Hence, it is not feasible to demo this application within the Metro-Haul project, notwithstanding that it will eventually become a reality and will be able to rely on the Metro-Haul network capabilities as a key enabler of these services.

2.2.5 Metro-Haul innovation to be validated

This scenario defines two key aspects that Metro-Haul can improve:

- Offered Traffic to network: Through NFV and in-node computing, the mIoT utility metering traffic can be reduced, providing improvements in bandwidth, link load, and link usage. Given the correct design and implementation of the in-node resources, the traffic pattern could be adapted to optical-oriented traffic, where meter-readings are accumulated and sent in a large burst rather than in smaller packets.
- User's QoE: The introduction of intermediate agents inserted by service providers would enable the QoE to be enhanced, since requests would be validated, and the agents can order the collection of new metrics in advance, so reducing the response time. Furthermore, potential actuators could also be activated upon the discovery of events by the intermediate agents, and so again reduce the response action time, whilst reducing traffic exchange in simple actuations.

2.2.6 Portability

mIoT utility metering is not a portable environment, as it comprises sensors taking measurements in multiple households. Furthermore, sensors in this scope are measuring different household utilities, such as water or gas consumption, which therefore introduces further portability problems. Finally, such utility consumption units, such as water taps, heaters or air conditioners need to be measured in massive volumes, which therefore also makes it unsuitable for a portable demo environment.

Even though a sub-set of such sensors could be easily transported and set up, there are still issues concerning the number of sensors that would be required to achieve optimal presentation of the Metro-Haul network capabilities, as well as problems concerning nearly-equal measurements.

2.3 Capacity planning of Content Delivery Network (CDN)

2.3.3 Brief description

As introduced in the project deliverable D2.1, Content Delivery Networks (CDNs) are networking solutions for efficiently handling the delivery of content, especially Video-on-Demand (VoD), to end users. A CDN is a geographically distributed network of caches aimed to locate "popular" (i.e. most-frequently-requested) contents closer to users, thus decreasing network traffic and improving users' QoE. High quality VoD already represents a huge percentage of the global consumer traffic, including

mobile data traffic. The optimization of cache deployment depends on various topological parameters (e.g. size of the metro transport network, location of the nodes), geotype area (e.g. urban, rural) and content characteristics (e.g. popularity distribution, size). In particular, to optimize a CDN and reduce network load, the popularity of the VoD content plays a significant role. This is known to follow a power law distribution, where a small portion of popular video contents account for a high percentage of video requests (short head) and a big portion of video contents account for a low percentage of requests (long tail). For example, an offload as high as 70% of video data from the metro/core network can be achieved by the caching of the most popular 10% of video contents of a given content provider at the edge nodes. CDNs can take advantage of the proposed Metro-Haul architecture, providing network edge nodes with storage and computing capabilities, enabling local cache and more efficient delivery of the required contents.

2.3.4 Feasibility

This feasibility study refers to the CDN scenario described in the project deliverable D2.1 and summarized, in terms of video-content catalogue and geotype, in Table 2.

Table 2 – CDN use case description

Content catalogue	10000 contents
Popularity distribution of the content catalogue.	Zipf distribution with skew parameter = 0.8
Size of contents	from 2 GB (short duration episodes) to 9 GB (long duration movies), following a power-law distribution with average size of 4.5 GB.
Max. n° of users (U_{max}) per second per AMEN	10000 (dense-urban geotype)
Average bit-rate b_r for video content	8 Mbps

At first, a conventional implementation of video contents caching in the metro segment is considered, where the 75% of the content catalogue (7500 contents, corresponding to popular contents which their popularity sums to 90%, i.e. hit ratio of 0.9) is cached in a single metro data centre hosting a video streaming service. The remaining 25%, corresponding to the less popular contents summing up to 10% popularity, are left in the remote video server located in the core network. Figure 1 shows the considered example.

Figure 1 – CDN capacity planning based on a single metro data centre (conventional scenario)

In the considered conventional case, as detailed in project deliverable D2.1, the required storage at the single metro data centre sums up to 33.75TB. In the peak hours, when up to half of all users are expected to request a video, the VoD service must be able to handle video traffic as high as 216 Gb/s, which can even reach up to 400 Gb/s and beyond in case of 4K/8K video.

In Metro-Haul, an alternative architecture is proposed and evaluated (see Figure 2). In particular, the CDN is proposed to be implemented by placing storage, computing and video streaming functionalities at both the AMEN and MCEN premises. In particular, each AMEN/MCEN includes storage, computing and video streaming functionalities, encompassing traffic inspection and video analytics to update the locally stored contents, according to which contents are more popular among users in the specific area.

Generic components and functionalities are:

- Contents data collection
- Storage (caching) of most popular contents
- Traffic inspection and Video Analytics
- Video streaming interfaces

By executing these tasks in the metro segment (i.e. directly in the AMEN and/or in the MCEN), video requests can be served at network edge (instead of at the remote video server), improving the QoS delivered to end-users. Required storage capacity is expected in the order of tens of TBs (per content provider), depending on the location of the node hosting the caching capability and on the percentage of video requests to be served. Real time traffic inspection is required to analyse and classify video contents and, most importantly, to discover which contents are popular among users in specific areas or to detect which contents are no longer popular and can be removed from the cache. Video streaming interface capacity essentially depends on the area demography and the traffic patterns and is generally in the order to tens of Gb/s, given by the maximum number of simultaneous users.

Figure 2 – CDN capacity planning in the Metro-Haul architecture (proposed scenario)

Caches in the CDN are designed to be able to satisfy 80% of the video requests (desired hit-ratio $H_{amen} = 0.8$). Therefore, the dimensioning of the cache (in terms of its size (GB) and video interfaces (Gb/s)) is done as follows:

- Storage capacity is calculated considering the popularity distribution formula, assuming the most popular contents, for which the overall popularity sums up to 80% (i.e. corresponding to hit-ratio of 0.8) are considered for caching. In the considered example, the number of contents which account for 80% of the requests is 5000 requiring a storage capacity of $SC_{amen} = 22.5\text{TB}$.
- For each AMEN, the required video interfaces are dimensioned according to the maximum amount of video traffic generated per second, i.e. considering the maximum number of users

simultaneously retrieving contents from the AMEN, U_{max} , the average bit-rate per user b_r , and the AMEN cache hit-ratio. Assuming half of all users request a video during the peak hour, the required video interface capacity $I_{amen} = 32$ Gb/s.

The remaining 20% of video requests are managed by the MCEN (for the most popular 10%) and by a remote video server, hosting the whole content provider video catalogue. MCEN storage capacity is dimensioned similarly to AMENs, targeting a hit ratio of 0.8, which, for typical content popularity distributions, corresponds to an overall popularity summing up to 10%, starting from the first content that is not cached in the AMEN (around 2500, ranging from 5001 to 7500), which corresponds in turn to a storage capacity required at the MCEN of around 11.25 TB. MCEN video-delivery throughput capacity must be enough to satisfy video requests of video contents stored/cached in the MCEN cache originated from users of all AMENs connected to the MCEN, and is computed to be $I_{mcen} = 24$ Gb/s.

Video traffic inspection is required at both AMEN and MCEN for all the video traffic passing through the nodes. With such caches deployment across the metro network nodes, while the AMEN inspects all video traffic generated by users connected to it, the MCEN inspects only the video traffic of requests not served by the AMEN. We consider the computing capacity of a deep packet inspection (DPI), performed by a DPI-engine, that is 10 Gb/s per core CPU. In the considered case study, the number of CPUs required at the AMEN and the MCEN is 4 and 5, respectively. Table 3 summarizes the network requirements of the selected tasks at both the AMEN and the MCEN for one content provider (one content catalogue).

Table 3 – Summary of Metro-Haul requirements for Content Delivery Network

Task	Throughput			Storage		Computing capacity	
	AMEN	MCEN	Optical	AMEN	MCEN	AMEN	MCEN
UHD/4K/8K video streaming	32Gb/s	24Gb/s	-	22.5TB	11.25TB	-	-
Video traffic inspection and analysis	40Gb/s	48Gb/s	10Gb/s ¹	-	-	4 vCPU	5 vCPU

2.2.3 Metro-Haul innovation

Three crucial tasks could be identified as performance bottlenecks, as they have stringent requirements:

- UHD/4K/8K video streaming for fixed and mobile users
- Peak-hour video streaming and flash crowd phenomenon
- Video-traffic inspection/monitoring and analysis

Metro-Haul architecture is able to support such challenging requirements, executing these crucial tasks directly in the metro segment. As seen, distributing the caching of the contents to AMENs and (partially) MCEN, i.e. closer to the users, in addition to functionalities such as monitoring, inspection and analysis of the transiting video traffic, allows to terminate video requests at network edge

1 Per content provider

(instead of the remote video server) strongly reducing the network load and improving the QoS delivered to end-users.

In WP5, Metro-Haul aims to experimentally demonstrate and validate the most relevant solutions designed by WP2 and developed in WP3 and WP4. The full validation of the capacity planning of CDN in the Metro-Haul solution described in Figure 2 and compared to the traditional case shown in Figure 1 would require the setup of significant resources mainly in terms of storage/caching and bandwidth resources. As anticipated, at the expenses of additional storage/caching capabilities placed at the AMENs, the main advantage of the proposed Metro-Haul CDN solution stands in the better scalability of the distributed VoD system, the lower latency offered to the customers, and a significant lower bandwidth required for CDN services along the metro network. Such advantages can be successfully evaluated at the design level in WP2. For this reason, and considering the large amount of resources potentially required for a complete validation, in WP5 the experimental validation of the proposed CDN capacity planning Metro-Haul solution is considered at low priority. That is, as detailed in this document, other solutions and use cases designed by WP2 are considered of higher relevance to better highlight the benefits of the whole Metro-Haul solution. Nevertheless, the validation of CDN services remains a high priority, as discussed in Section 3.3.

2.3.5 Portability

The capacity planning CDN solution considered in this section is considered not suitable for portable validations given the large amount of involved network and IT resources. However, the CDN service and more specifically some software components to support it, in a fully controlled and orchestrated way, can be considered for portability, also in combination with software modules suitable for other use cases (see for example next section on live TV distribution).

2.4 Live TV distribution

2.4.3 Brief description

Live-TV distribution is one of the stringent and more popular services that a telecom network needs to support. To allow adapting live TV to a wide range of qualities, uncompressed video streaming formats are used; uncompressed video streaming supporting 4K UHD TV format ranges from 6 to 48 Gb/s. Those uncompressed video streams are then processed and adapted to compressed streams for video distribution, requiring up to hundreds Mb/s per individual user depending on its quality, i.e. standard definition (SD), high definition (HD) or ultra HD (UHD).

Video signal processing can be performed in commodity hardware inside metro DCs placed closer to end-users. Therefore, uncompressed UHD video signals need to be conveyed from the signal source to each of the metro DCs including computing resources for video processing. Those resources for live TV processing are called *leaf caches*. Assuming that the standardized MPEG Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (MPEG-DASH) technique is used, multimedia contents can be served by HTTP servers. A cache component named packager is in charge of generating MPEG-DASH segments with several qualities, hence performing video trans-coding/trans-rating. A virtualized leaf cache node would be composed of packagers, HTTP server, and a cache manager all running as software inside VMs in the metro DC, where each component consists of a resource pool for load balancing and redundancy purposes.

One of the main benefits of using a dynamic, adaptive virtualized infrastructure is the capability of fitting time-varying demand requirements without incurring into expensive resource overprovisioning. Therefore, data-driven operation and management (OAM) of virtualized

components is mandatory, leveraging both monitoring data from network and computing resources and user-related QoE metrics.

In this regard, local, e.g. at computing nodes, and global (network-wide) re-optimization can be applied to reduce resource utilization while ensuring the highest quality to end users. Data stream mining, regression and machine learning techniques can also be used to produce estimation of future scenarios for such re-optimization processes.

2.4.4 Feasibility

A demonstrator of live TV distribution is available at UPC’s lab (see Figure 3). The virtualized leaf cache node includes HTTP servers, MPEG-DASH packagers, and a cache manager, all components running inside VMs deployed in the same DC. The cache manager is the entry point of the cache node; it receives users’ requests, identifies which contents will be locally stored, and redirects users’ requests to the appropriate HTTP server. A centralized CDN Admission and Control module implements CDN access policies and redirects users’ requests, e.g. based on their geographical location, to the (intermediate or leaf) cache node that will serve them.

Figure 3 – Live TV distribution

The CDN Manager (Figure 4) is responsible for adapting the CDN to the current and future load. The Monitoring and Data Analytics (MDA) system includes data collection, pre-processing, and storage and allows applications to monitor and manage allocated resources, while protecting the privacy and integrity of data. Hence, the performance and load of a CDN can be monitored to elastically adapt its resources to current service needs.

A configuration manager is in charge of interfacing the VIM to request and release resources and of properly configuring each cache node. After processing collected data from the MDA system, it can be used to predict likely scenarios, thus anticipating future demand load distribution. A prediction module based on machine learning and time series modelling is proposed to that end.

Based on current and future load, the CDN can be optimized to minimize total costs while serving live-TV contents to the end users ensuring the highest QoE level. To that aim, three optimization problems have been devised. Analyzing current and predicted load distribution, a decision maker module is responsible of triggering the most appropriate optimization problem as well as selecting meaningful input data for its solving.

Figure 4 – Live TV management based on monitoring and data analytics

2.4.5 Metro-Haul innovation to be validated

UPC’s live TV distribution demonstrator can be used to show the following components of the Metro-Haul architecture defined in WP4:

- Interface IO-4 with the MDA system.
- Interface IO-3 with the service orchestrator.
- Service re-configuration based on monitored data.

2.4.6 Portability

The demonstrator is portable in its current version, as no networking is considered. Live-TV distribution towards the users is available and it can be demonstrated.

2.5 Service Robotics

2.5.3 Brief description

The International Organization for Standardization defines a “service robot” as a robot “that performs useful tasks for humans or equipment excluding industrial automation applications” [1]. In Metro-Haul D2.1 a use case named service robotics is extensively presented and in particular the concepts of Cloud Robotics Infrastructure (CRI) is introduced [2]. Figure 5 shows the CRI architecture. The CRI allows a robot to maintain on-board, in the location where the robot operates, the hardware (sensors, actuators), the basic control logic and the communication software (in Figure 5 on the left), while leaving the most demanding software tasks to a server in a remote location (in a specific data centre or even in the cloud, in Figure 5 on the right). The communication network, composed by a fixed part and a radio part for the mobile connection of the robot, is in the middle of Figure 5, between the robot and CRI services. Metro Haul can play a key role in this model as Metro segment is an important portion of the fixed part of communication network used by cloud service robotics. In addition, part of the CRI, for a given application or family of applications, could be installed in computation and storage resources of Metro-Haul nodes (in the paradigm Node as a Data Centre) and made available as Virtual Machines.

Figure 5 – A simplified model for HW and SW systems, computational tasks and communication in Service robotics.

Applications of service robotics are wide and involve many aspects of human life and have countless applications in Industry (automation apart) and Services. A first classification distinguishes between terrestrial and flying robots. Among flying robots, the Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), also known as drones, are one of the fields in which TIM Innovation department currently focuses its researches and lab experiments. The following of this section describes the current experiments already demonstrated in TIM Innovation Labs and discuss a development towards their possible integration with Metro-Haul architecture.

2.5.4 Feasibility

What is available now in TIM Innovation Labs is the experiment shown in Figure 6. The service Robotics infrastructure is installed in the Azure Microsoft Cloud and it includes both Application manager and Controller, including the instances to control the robots. The Drone is connected with an LTE mobile connection and, via the public internet, to the Cloud where its controller is running. Due to the type of interconnections and the resulting latency, control strategies requiring a fast or ultra-fast responses cannot be implemented.

Figure 6 – Picture that shows the experiment as it is.

Some drones have been equipped with a mobile connection through which their autopilot can send telemetry and receive commands. The drones have also a camera sending a live stream through the same mobile connection.

In this way a number of proof of concepts have been developed belonging basically to two main classes: 1) applications for drone monitoring in the national airspace, 2) drones controlled by a centralized command center for “eye in the sky” applications. The first class of applications requires a high level of reliability and scalability because all drones must be monitored at the same time and possibly first warned and then forced out of sensitive areas. The second class requires low latency for commands and high bandwidth for video streams.

These drones are compliant to current Italian regulations issued by ENAC (Italian Civil Aviation Authority) and their characteristics allow them to fly in urban areas.

Figure 7 – Possible experiment over the Metro-Haul architecture.

A development from the already available experiment described above to a new Metro-Haul relevant experiment is depicted in Figure 7. The LTE mobile access is replaced by a 5G access prototype. In addition the Service Robotics Infrastructure is split into two subsets. In particular this experiment: i) leave the Application manager in the remote cloud, and ii) move the Controller, with its application instances, in the metro node closest to the drone (or to the drones). Thus that allowing: 1) better performances on both latency and bandwidth, 2) scalability (potentially, due to the distributed model, no limits will exist on the number of drones controlled by the CRI).

It is under evaluation to perform the experiments leveraging the FutureNet test-bed (Figure 8).

Figure 8 – TIM's FutureNet test-bed

The test-bed is composed of 4 aggregation nodes and one metro node based on CORD (Central Office Re-architected as a Data Centre). Every node has both forwarding and compute capabilities that could be exploited for running the drone controlling applications; one of the aggregation nodes is dedicated to mobile access allowing, therefore, interconnection with the drone. All nodes are then interconnected by means of a disaggregated optical network employing ONOS as SDN controller; a service orchestrator (currently under definition) is in charge of coordinating networking and computing functions of the nodes for the realization of end-to-end services.

2.5.5 Metro-Haul innovation to be validated

The main innovation achievable by the proposed experiment is the use of a metro node (assuming the paradigm of Node as a DC) to install as VF/VMs the robot Controller of the CRI and the single Application instances to control the drones. Measurement of latency and bandwidth could be performed to verify the achievable performance with this architecture.

2.5.6 Portability

This experiment, as it is now, is not portable outside of Italy because of different national regulations for drones. This makes difficult to develop drone solutions readily usable in different countries. Moreover possible demos in Italy must be compliant to ENAC regulations and arranged in suitable areas, such as the city park in Turin where the applications have been developed and tested. In addition we are not able to foresee the availability of 5G prototypes mobile infrastructure at the time of the experiment (second half of 2019, beginning 2020).

On the other hand using simulated drones in a Gazebo simulator connected to the CRI, in principle the experiment is portable everywhere there is a network infrastructure compliant with Metro-Haul architecture (5G mobile access plus nodes compliant with Metro-Haul architecture).

2.6 Smart Factory

2.6.3 Brief description

The use cases related to the smart factory represent the introduction of the Internet and IoT technologies within the manufacturing processes. They rely heavily on the cyber physical systems

(CPSs) or smart devices. A CPS can be both the evolution of the current programmable logic controller (PLC) and new type of sensors and actuators, including robots. Automated guided vehicles are assumed to be extensively used for material transfer. Video cameras for quality monitoring and surveillance are also present. The goal of this use case is to create a smart factory, modular and in islands, which can be remotely controlled. The Smart Factory has a virtual image in the internet cyber world. IoT technologies help the smart devices to communicate and cooperate with each other and with humans in real time.

Regarding the impact on communications, and in particular as regard the role of the 5G network, the model is articulated into two levels:

- **Intra-factory:** it involves the communication within the systems and machineries inside the plant. From 5G communication point of view it involves local data exchanges and all the needs should remain closed within the reference local edge node (e.g. AMEN). The radio access segment and related requirements is fundamental for the intra-factory communication. 5G is the candidate to replace a costly and rigid cabling system and it competes with other local private wireless network (for communication) and IT (for the cloud part) solutions.
- **Inter-factory:** it concerns the communication between plants and with Headquarters, which coordinates the whole production system. This communication in general involves both the metro segment (involving AMEN and MCEN) and the core- network (between MCENs).

The smart factory use case can be more appropriately defined as a non-exhaustive collection of a set of sub use cases, each having its own service requirements. For the 5G network, the aggregated demand to be carried on and the set of requirements to be fulfilled come from the whole set of heterogeneous types of services. Components of a Smart factory that are taken into consideration for the Intra-factory model are:

- Robots
- PLC lines (or their evolution)
- Sensors for process monitoring
- Video cameras (ultra-high definition) for quality check
- Video cameras (high definition) for plant surveillance
- Automated guided vehicles for material transportation
- Factory Application Platforms

The crucial tasks in a Smart Factory use case are:

- Motion Control
- HD Video Surveillance Communication and Processing
- UHD Video Quality Check Communication and Processing
- Sensors' connections and data processing
- Factory coordination processes

The impact of these crucial tasks on the metro network KPIs are important and are listed below.

- High transmission capacity & AMEN/MCEN throughput
- Low latency and packet jitter
- High Availability
- Large storage capacity at AMEN
- High computational capacity at AMEN
- Transmission degradation detection

- VM monitoring
- Failure detection and very fast network protection/restoration

2.6.4 Feasibility

Metro-Haul is not planning to develop processes specific for this use case, and an access network is also out of scope of the project. Therefore the Metro-Haul network KPIs that are being developed overlapping with the list above is the high capacity of the optical metro network, traffic monitoring and degradation detection, and fast network protection/restoration.

Network protection over access and metro networks involves the connection between some point in the access network through two geographically remote AMEN, and through two diverse routes connected to a single MCEN. Note that network connection protection could involve the whole route between the Smart Factory and another location where e.g. the Factory (aggregated) Headquarters are sited (assuming for example one Headquarters location and a different remote production plant locations).

The traffic monitoring could provide the means to trigger/start the route switching, and the SDN controller could participate in a number of tasks:

- Computation of the end-to-end primary and protection path configuration over the metro and access networks and over two remote AMEN
- Analyse the information from the traffic monitoring system
- Trigger/start the protection switching according to pre-established criteria (e.g. complete failure, degradation above a set threshold, etc.)

Figure 9 – Illustration of protected connection over metro/access using optical/Ethernet layers for the Smart Factory use case

2.6.5 METRO-HAUL innovation to be validated

The main aspects to be validated are

- The use of the SDN/controller to calculate and establish a protected connection
 - o over 2/3 different networks (metro, access, and maybe radio)
 - o over different network layers (optical and Ethernet)
- The use of the SDN/controller to trigger the protection/restoration
- Reconfigurable, high capacity optical metro network

2.6.6 Portability

The possibility of building a portable demonstration, though possible, is very hard because of the need to build three nodes (2 AMEN and 1 MCEN), i.e. hardware, along with the optical network nodes. The controller/orchestrator should be easier to build and demonstrate since it is software.

2.7 6DoF Virtual Reality

2.7.3 Brief description

Extended Reality (XR) is the Next-generation VR (Virtual Reality), and encompasses both AR (Augmented Reality) and MR (Mixed Reality) experiences. It will have 6 degree of freedom (6DoF) allowing users to move within the environment. 6DoF content is an order of magnitude richer in naturalness and interactivity than 3 degrees of freedom (3DoF) video. Current 3DoF experiences, such as 360° video, allow the user to rotationally look around from a fixed position. 6DoF experiences (available in video-games today), will allow the user wearing a Head-Mounted Display (HMD) to move spatially through the environment just by walking or leaning the head forward.

Head movement while wearing an HMD with head tracking is a specific interaction with very strict latency requirements. Motion-to-photon (MTP) latency is the time between an action (a head movement) and reaction (the display is updated based on the movement). A MTP latency below 20ms is currently targeted for many VR user experiences, but studies have shown that achieving a MTP latency of less than 15ms makes the delay imperceptible to nearly all users. Therefore it is expected that AR and VR applications will keep MTP processing on the device (the HMD itself). There are hybrid-computing scenarios where 3D rendering happens off the device. PCs and game consoles tethered to VR HMDs are available today, while network edge or cloud rendering may be possible in the future. For these hybrid scenarios, ABI research expects that the processing will be intelligently split between cloud-based 3D rendering, which requires low network latency, and additional processing on the untethered mobile device to ensure high quality visuals at a fixed low MTP latency.

Among all the possible 6DoF XR services we look at an immersive experience that allows the user to virtually move within a **live event** (for instance within a stadium during a football match) by means of VR HMD 5G mobile connected.

The identified service implies the following components and data processing tasks:

- VR head-mounted display 5G mobile connected and worn by the user (high bandwidth and strict latency requirements).
- VIDEO collection and processing at the location of the event. A local server produces the VR immersive video streaming flow to be transmitted to the Edge server (very high bandwidth).
- RT Video Content Server makes VR immersive video streaming available to the user taking into account the HMD movement (high bandwidth and strict latency requirements)

This use case has the following impact on the Metro Haul architecture:

EDGE (AMEN), which hosts Local source of 6DoF VR interactive streams, will require high processing, storage and data rate capacities for the local video server that have to receive the 6DoF VR immersive live streaming from the event location ($\approx 2-10$ Gb/s) and make the dedicated streaming instances available to the end users ($N \times 100/600$ Mb/s, on average, where N is the number of simultaneous users served by the edge node, for $N=100 \rightarrow 10/60$ Gb/s).

EVENT LOCATION (MCEN or AMEN) will necessitate server with a very high processing capacity, which produces the VR immersive video stream ($\approx 2-10$ Gb/s) and transmits them to the edge nodes by a multicast scheme.

The crucial tasks identified for the 6DoF VR use case are the following three:

- Local Source processing at the user's local AMEN and interactive VR stream delivering to the HMD.
- Original Source processing at the remote AMEN or MCEN near where the event takes place.
- High data rate and reliable multicast communication over the core and metro networks between the original source node (AMEN or MCEN) and all the local source nodes (AMENs) where service users are located. Note that this task might involve a number of core networks or none if the event and the users are located very far apart or in the same metro area respectively.

The resulting network KPIs for this use case are:

- Massive storage capacity and computation capability at the Original remote node (AMEN or MCEN)
- Very high storage capacity and computation capability at the local user node (AMEN).
- Very high optical multicast transmission between MCEN and AMEN between 10-100 Gb/s
- Dynamic connection re-configuration across the metro network
- Transmission degradation detection
- VM monitoring and dynamic reconfiguration
- Failure detection and very fast network protection/restoration

2.7.4 Feasibility

The 6DoF VR is a multicast service with a very high bandwidth required per connection. This service would greatly benefit from a dynamic optical layer at the metro. Of special relevance would be to use multicast functionality within the optical layer.

In order to achieve the required functionality, the SDN controller needs to be orchestrating the service end-to-end with open interfaces onto the optical metro nodes.

The Metro-Haul Project could build a Proof of Concept limiting the scope within the metro network between an MCEN and an AMEN configuring the necessary functionality (or an example of the functionality) of the VM in both nodes. The PoC could then add another service stream between the MCEN and another AMEN, using the multicast capability of the optical nodes (being developed in WP 3). Using such capability would help reducing the necessary capacity in the metro network.

This is illustrated in the following figure. End-User a requested the service in the first place and the controller configured the connection through the metro network over optical nodes X and Y. later End-user b joined the service. In order to minimise the network capacity needed, the controller uses the multicast capability of the optical nodes to connect Node X to Node Z via Node Y.

Figure 10 – Illustration of multicast connection over metro/access using optical layer for the 6DoF VR use case

Another aspect of the Metro-Haul architecture that could be demonstrated would be resilience, analogous to the Smart Factory use case, where a failed connection is restored through the adjacent AMEN to which the end user may be connected.

The controller might want to reconfigure the multicast connections if the traffic conditions change in order to optimise the usage of the metro network capacity. In order to implement this functionality successfully, the service quality should not be impacted and thus the end-users' service experience should be unaffected by the reconfiguration. The buffered traffic cannot introduce a delay that is deemed too long for a live event streaming, and therefore any reconfiguration should happen a) be within the latency introduced by the traffic buffering at the AMEN, and b) allow some level of buffering at the AMEN after the reconfiguration has taken place.

2.7.5 Metro-Haul innovation to be validated

There are a number of innovative functionalities that could be validated with such a Proof of Concept.

- the use of the SDN/controller developed in WP4, to calculate and establish a multicast connection over the optical network by directly controlling the optical nodes being developed in WP3
- The use of the SDN/controller to add another end-user and calculate the new connection taking into account the existing end-users and minimising the overall network capacity being used
- Reconfigurable, high capacity optical metro network

2.7.6 Portability

The possibility of building a portable demonstration, though possible, is very hard because of the need to build three nodes (2 AMEN and 1 MCEN), i.e. hardware, along with the optical network nodes. The controller/orchestrator should be easier to build and demonstrate since it is software.

2.8 Intelligent Transport System and Autonomous Driving

2.8.3 Brief description

Most major car manufacturing companies are currently working to bring Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) to the market within 2025. In fact, some companies such as Waymo, are already starting to deploy

pilot programs where AVs play a key role for ride-sharing services². Indeed, AVs themselves will require very large network requirements, as it is estimated that an AV generates on average about 4,000 GB a day³.

Furthermore, related technologies will appear to complement and enhance AV functionalities, namely intelligent environments, which incorporate into the urban street furniture different sensors and actuators that are able to collect information from their surroundings and inform nearby AVs of potential dangers and events.

Both AVs and intelligent driving environments will have stringent requirements in terms of bandwidth, guaranteed QoS and low latency, which can be enabled by the Metro-Haul network, both in communications with/between service data-centers, and between the self-driving entities.

2.8.4 Feasibility

The scenario for Vehicle-to-Vehicle/Infrastructure (V2X) communications poses several challenges to be demonstrated in any demo. It requires the availability of AVs and other sensors that need low-latency and high capacity communications as well as synchronization. Hence, a valid demonstration scenario would require a relatively large urban setting where most of the urban furniture would need to have sensors installed, as well as a few AVs that can drive around the urban environment.

Hence, this use case is not particularly appropriate to be demonstrated in Metro-Haul, as most of the key elements are still in the test-driving phase: there is no AV on the market as yet, and most components in the network are still in the research phase despite the rapid advances that are occurring. Furthermore, the deployment of a prototype with such characteristics would be time-consuming and expensive, even when not considering the legal and political implications.

For this purpose, this use case is an example of an important future application of the Metro-Haul network; but which will arrive when all the technology has been developed and is in production. Meanwhile, there are more convenient and illustrative use cases of the Metro-Haul network that can be demonstrated to show its potential.

2.8.5 Metro-Haul innovation to be validated

Innovation achievable through this experiment would be to install VF/VMs on either the AMEN or MCENs and demonstrate how well the Metro-Haul architecture performs when dealing with a large number of AVs interchanging such an amount of information with the cloud.

A set of measurement-based experiments considering the bandwidth, latency and jitter would be required to check whether or not the Metro-Haul network complies with the performance metrics demanded by this challenging use case.

2.8.6 Portability

The portability of this scenario is very limited due to its size, and the requirements within the demonstration site. The setup is large and needs to be embedded within a relatively dense urban environment, which makes portability a secondary issue. Furthermore, sensor networks composing

2 See <http://www.businessinsider.com/waymo-self-driving-uber-competitor-arizona-2017-11>

3 See <https://www.networkworld.com/article/3147892/internet/one-autonomous-car-will-use-4000-gb-of-dataday.html>

the intelligent driving environment are made of sensors embedded into the urban street furniture, which also greatly complicates the installation and recovery of such sensors.

Finally, in general, AVs are cars, which tend to be oversized and heavier due to their required on-board systems, and are therefore difficult and costly to be transported for demonstrations.

2.9 Enterprise Access with NG Ethernet

2.9.3 Brief description

Large enterprises (e.g. Banks) need very high bandwidth and low latency access to the Metro Network to support their needs to operate their IT infrastructure. For example, some common services with these requirements include:

- Interconnect two Data Centres (DCs) (primary and secondary) or a private and a public cloud, as well as central premises. This is a clear case of high bandwidth consumption (several tens of Gb/s). In fact, an expensive dark fibre is usually contracted for this.
- High available large databases, with low delay and high bandwidth interconnections for data replication. In this case, low delay is needed to keep data base coherence with synchronous replication. A similar case would be the replication of a disk enclosure.

Given the latency requirements (see below), such connections could be classified as ultra-reliable low latency (URLLC).

To provide such access, it is common that network operators provide a router with a standard interface at the edge of the enterprise premises. Current link standard is clearly Ethernet, with speeds ranging from 10 Mbps to 400 Gb/s. Flex Ethernet has also been proposed [3]. Current high speed Ethernet interfaces are flexible. For instance, a 100 Gb/s interface can be configured as: 1x100 Gb/s, 1x40 Gb/s, 4x25 Gb/s, or 4x10 Gb/s interfaces.

Given the cost of such high bandwidth and low delay service, large enterprises need to check the SLA related to the service they are paying to the operator. Thus, it is necessary to check both capacity and delay, as well as availability and reliability provided by the network between Data Centres, connected to the network through new Ethernet flexible standards. Both active and passive monitoring probes are advisable for this task, which make this use case a good scenario where to test Naudit's probes to be developed at Metro-Haul.

2.9.4 Feasibility

Naudit is involved in WP3 and WP4 in the development of passive and active network measurement probes working at 100 Gb/s. These probes are useful to check the SLA, as described above. Thus, in WP5 such probes can be demonstrated in a scenario where 100 Gb/s Ethernet interfaces are used both to capture and to send traffic to measure capacity, delay and packet losses.

For the passive probe, it is necessary to have a traffic source working at high rate. In this case, we can use a traffic generator, developed also by Naudit, which will feed the passive probe as if it were in a SPAN port of a Metro Haul node. For the active probe, it is necessary that the equipment or network to be measured has 100 GbE interface. It is expected that other partners can provide such standard high rate interfaces.

2.9.5 Metro-Haul innovation to be validated

Metro-Haul network architecture is envisioned to provide access not only to mobile users, but also to large enterprises, which currently are interconnected with expensive dark fibres. Thus, the innovation in this use case is manifold:

1. Provide large capacity Ethernet interfaces (100 Gb/s and above) to large companies that have to access to the metro network.
2. Provide very low latency for data replication services (databases, disks enclosures) of these large companies.
3. Provide VPN or VLAN extension services for those large companies by using network slicing.

Moreover, the innovation to be validated will also be related to the monitoring aspects of the Metro Haul network, from a Layer 2 and Layer 3 perspective, dealing with the development and validation of high rate probes working at 100 Gb/s with standard Ethernet interfaces. These probes are crucial for large companies, because they can be used to assess that the provided service gives them the required throughput, latency and connectivity, thus validating the innovations defined in this use case. Other innovations from other partners' developments can also be validated with these network probes, provided that they have standard 100GbE interfaces.

2.9.6 Portability

Naudit has specified and acquired for the project a small form factor server (see Figure 11) a network traffic generator with a 100 GbE NIC and four NVMe drives to store traffic traces. It is about 43.7x43cm and 1U (4.3 cm) height, so it is somehow portable, although it cannot travel in a plane cabin due to its weight.

Figure 11 – Small form factor server for traffic generation

The FPGA development (see Figure 12) is, however, not as portable as the server described above. It comprises several cards, and it is a very fragile equipment to be transported to other locations easily. It comprises a mezzanine board with 10x10GbE interfaces (left side of Figure 12) connected with an FMC adaptor, the FPGA board (middle of Figure 12) is in this case a VCU-108 from Xilinx (a VCU-118 will also be used), and a SoM-PC to control and program the FPGA (right side of Figure 12) with a PCIe adaptor.

Figure 12 – FPGA development.

Finally, a special transportation case (Peli Storm iM2875) has been acquired in order to transport these developments safely.

2.10 Crowdsourced video broadcasts

2.10.3 Brief description

Consider a sporting event in a crowded stadium. Often, spectators will film on their smartphones, later posting these videos to YouTube, Facebook, etc. Even if their content is generally mundane, these videos capture the unique perspective of the observer, and views potentially missed by professional videographers, even if present. Unfortunately, given a multitude of sources, such video content is difficult to browse and search.

Crowdsourced live streaming (CLS) platforms allow general users to broadcast their content to massive viewers, thereby greatly expanding the content and user bases. CLS services enriches social interactions across communities by allowing users to share common interests and stories, Furthermore, if organisations hosting such events could easily capture all those video content in an interactive and highly shareable visual story about the event this would boost its social reach immensely.

Services like Watchity, Periscope etc. provide such cloud based CLS systems to extract content-specific metadata from crowd sourced videos which identifies and forms a “clusters” of synchronized streams with related content surrounding the event. These clusters are made available online so that event organisers can capture different views and combine them to portray their brand or message.

But synchronizing such large, high volume streams and capturing them at a cloud service require a high capacity network infrastructure which adapts and scales dynamically to accommodate multiple synchronized streams. Moreover, the heterogeneous quality, format and information of source stream require computational resource to transcode it into multiple industrial standard quality

versions to serve viewers with distinct configurations requiring computing capability close to the source of videos.

2.10.3.1 Crowdsourced video broadcasting workflow and components

Figure 13 – Crowdsourced video broadcasting workflow and components

- Capture devices (smartphones with GPS, Compass, Accelerometer, Gyroscope) upload content along with sensor data through the crowdsource video sharing application
- The video app will analyse the content and its associated data (location, position, angle) to filter and aggregate multiple videos into clusters
- As the clusters increase the video application tries to optimise the clustered streams based on their position and content. The app will request the network orchestrator to provide computing resources and low latency path to these computing resources to aggregate and synchronize its video streams. Service orchestrator converts this request and feeds it to respective controllers to provide edge compute resources.
- The crowd source video APP will also request orchestrator, via APIs, for high capacity network paths to reach the cloud provider where the clustered videos will be further edited and be prepared for consumption by users. Orchestrator will translate the request to network requirements and feed the path setup configurations to involved device controllers.

Example here from our application partner Watchity, which is a platform for crowdsourced live video content in which an organization can capture videos from a multitude of users recorded with any device. Watchity allows the organization to issue a combined live multi-camera video that can display multiple views on one single event, events or place. The core of the platform is a technology for the capturing, generating, distributing and reproducing of multi-camera videos. To watch it in action, please go to: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LK6aKb3VnEg&feature=youtu.be>.

2.10.4 Feasibility

2.10.4.1 Crowdsourcing application requirements

The application runs on a smartphone which has ability to create an event, stream videos and watch other associated video streams. Users can access the cloud serviced app to aggregate/segregate streams and edit them on the fly to be consumed by users like event owners, spectators etc. Later users like venue owners can use it to make their own videos or use it for promotion purposes. Crowdsourcing application has following high level infrastructure requirement

- High density of users, with the application on smartphones, to stream videos

- To get a 360 view of the entire event
- Connectivity to cloud services from the smartphone
 - High bandwidth for aggregated video streams
 - Jitter and loss free video paths
- Computing nodes for video processing
 - Processing power to run algorithms to cluster co-related(same geo-area) video streams

2.10.4.2 Metro-Haul requirements:

To satisfy application connectivity requirements Metro-Haul nodes need to do the following:

At the AMEN/Metro network it will be necessary to have:

- Computing capability at AMEN to process video and sensor data to aggregate and form clusters of crowd videos
- Dynamic high capacity paths to upload clustered video streams. Data rates of ~10Gbps for a 30K capacity stadium
- Monitor and gather video application requirements and provide network services.
- Provide virtual load layer4/7 load balancers, content caching, compression and TCP/IP multiplexing

At the MCEN/Core network it will be necessary to have:

- Processing power to identify individual video clusters to provide paths to different datacentre facilities
- Multiple routes (upload/download multi-path TCP) to reach video application data centre
- Monitor and gather video application requirements and provide network services. E.g. Jitter, bandwidth, as the number of video clusters allocate more paths to different cloud locations
- Provide load balancing, between multiple data centre routes, to manage scale

2.10.4.3 Current demonstration network

The use case will be demonstrated over the Ashton Gate Stadium at Bristol, UK. The stadium is multi-venue stadia used for football/rugby matches, exhibitions and conference. It's a 27000-spectator capacity stadium and it's the largest venue in the southwest region. The stadium consists of following infrastructure

- 52 stacked 10G switches forming a star topology
- 160 wireless access points serving >12000 concurrent users on the WiFi
- 150 LED screens for advertisements
- More than 15 subsystems like CCTV, POS etc., supporting stadium operations

The WiFi network is associated with >10000 clients on a match day and this is where the network problems occur for crowd sourced applications i.e. scaling users.

Figure 14 – Stadium LAN view through Zeetta's SDN controller

2.10.4.4 Metro-Haul node placement

Access-Metro-Edge Node (AMEN) nodes will be placed at the gateway device where the stadium LAN connects to WAN via ISP link. Multiple of 10G network, combination of wireless and wired links, connect to the AMEN node which will provide processing power for clustering and tagging of video streams along with bandwidth for aggregating traffic.

With the help of local ISP a MCEN node will be placed at the nearest point-of-presence (POP) where the MCEN will monitor, aggregate video streams, and make forwarding decisions to cloud video servers on behalf of the application.

Figure 15 – Node placement

2.10.4.5 Scenarios to test:

On minimum load: The crowd source streaming APP will form clusters (tagged video streams) and request the Orchestrator, via Intent APIs, for high capacity network paths to reach the cloud provider. Orchestrator will translate the request to network requirements and feed the path setup configurations to involved device controllers.

On average load: As the clusters increase the APP will request the orchestrator to provide computing resources and low latency path to these computing resources to aggregate and synchronize its video streams as close as possible to the sources. Orchestrator converts this request and feeds it to respective controllers to provide edge compute resources along with low latency paths.

On high load: As the clusters increase massively the Orchestrator monitoring services will identify the increase and install a load balancer to balance the load across the network.

2.10.5 Metro-Haul innovation to be validated

2.10.5.1 Metro-Haul Node capability (WP3)

- High bandwidth capable metro nodes (AMEN)
- Metro nodes with computing capability on the fly to aggregate and form clusters of crowd videos at the access network
- Provide multiple dynamic high capacity paths to upload clustered video streams (MCEN)

2.10.5.2 Network Orchestrator capabilities to host the service (WP4)

- Dynamically allocate high bandwidth paths based on clustered video bandwidths
- Platform to monitor and gather video application requirements and provide network services. E.g. as the number of video clusters allocate more paths to different cloud locations
- Optimise network based on jitter and latency parameters
- Platform to provide virtual load balancers. Capabilities include layer4/7 load balancing, content caching and compression, TCP/IP multiplexing.

2.10.6 Portability

The demonstration is not portable, but the application can be redeployed at another location e.g. BT premises for demonstrations.

2.11 Real-time low-latency object tracking

2.11.3 Brief description

Public surveillance CCTV systems have been proven to be a cost-effective security solution to reduce and document crime. As such, Humbolt park in San Francisco, where savings on crime related costs were four times higher than the investment in CCTV systems [4], or London, which presented 50% cost savings per year [5], serve as good examples.

Video analytics can have a great impact on conventional CCTV systems and bring intelligence by incorporating detection and alert algorithms. With video analytics it is now possible to identify faces, various objects vehicles, bags and public threats automatically. Combining video analytics with conventional CCTV systems enables new use cases such related to security such as identification and tracking of a wide range of subjects, counting and measuring speed and direction of movement. By defining various patterns, alarms can be triggered based on rules and perimeter detection such as presence of large vehicles in controlled areas, unattended bags left in crowded zones, or large number of people running from/towards a specific direction. Such software can have great implications on designing an automated, integrated and city wide security system with increased efficiency for control room operation.

Novel 5G Metro-Haul technology developed within the project is showcased in a future smart city scenario, where security is provided by real-time object recognition and tracking. Simultaneous real-time access to the data of several fixed and mobile cameras allows tracking of objects and persons as well as the automatic recognition of critical events which encompass areas larger than the field of view of a single camera (e.g., population density). Mobile cameras may be body cams or mounted on drones connected to nearby base stations depending on the specific application scenario. The number of used cameras and their data rate can be flexibly adapted to the situation and resource availability at hand.

Figure 16 – Functional block placement for the Real-time low-latency object tracking use case

2.11.4 Feasibility

A geo-distributed architecture tailored for low-response times and high-bandwidth requirements will be implemented based on the previously proposed architecture in Milestone 2.1. At the core of the deployment is a CORD setup with a head node and multiple compute nodes. An overview of the architecture including the fundamental functional blocks is illustrated in Figure 16. The head node separating the OpenStack control services, the SDN controller (e.g., ONOS) and the CORD controller (XOS) into Linux containers, is deployed in the MCEN. Through OpenStack and ONOS, XOS will be able to orchestrate the local (MCEN) and remote (AMEN) resources and assume the role of accomplishing Virtual Function Chaining.

The setup will allow us to demonstrate the following:

- A video surveillance system with RT object tracking, automated face recognition and handover between various flexible camera devices. While a recognition algorithm (face or specific object) will act as a trigger for detecting a subject by a specific fixed camera, a RT low latency handover to a variable camera (e.g., PTZ or mobile) will occur for subject tracking as it moves away from the field of view of the first one.
 - Due to low latency requirements for RT video analytics, initial video processing occurs in the AMEN. Functionality for controlling auto-tracking of Pan-Tilt-Zoom (PTZ) and mobile cameras is envisioned here as well.
 - Video stream distribution: video flows are transported from the UEs to the designated AMEN for initial real-time low-latency object tracking and backhauled towards the core DC for storage. Metadata extracted is sent for further processing towards the MCEN. Various events (e.g., subject identification, pattern disturbances) can trigger the chance of video quality streaming for extracting additional information with the purpose of conserving bandwidth utilization and storage capacity. Client streams will be viewable in a centralized location (MCEN) or on mobile devices upon request.
- Low-latency connectivity between fixed and mobile cameras assigned to the same AMEN
- Enable flexible distributed cloud computing capabilities for real-time dynamic object tracking applications
- Demonstration of a comprehensive SDN-based network and DC control utilizing standardized open APIs
 - Based on an open platform architecture, the proposed implementation will combine edge computing, CORD (Central Office Re-Architected as Data Centre) and cloud

computing. Virtualization enables multi-tenancy while dynamic provision of location, capacity and latency information allows to optimally map services to the available resources. Standardized interfaces shall provide simple integration of stationary and mobile user equipment.

- The management of the platform uses SDN-based network control as well as computing and storage resources. An orchestrator application will allow the setup and end-to-end management of distributed software functions. Open APIs will enable coordination between the application layer and the infrastructure layer of the platform.

2.11.5 Metro-Haul innovation to be validated

This use case will demonstrate the embedment and support of a video surveillance application in a 5G Metro-Haul network scenario and its SDN-based orchestration. It shall showcase the solution's capability to exchange real-time data aggregation from multiple sources and to store and compute within appropriate DC resources. Novel low-latency networks and distributed edge computing concepts enable machine-to-machine and human-machine interactions, which are not yet possible with current technology. Multi-tenancy support will be demonstrated with the help of the CORD architecture deployed in the AMEN and MCEN locations. Operator orchestration of bare-metal devices including networking, storage and computing capabilities will be possible with the use of a centralized CORD orchestrator (i.e., XOS) allowing for service function chaining of the various components in the video security system.

2.11.6 Portability

As the setup will include an open platform based on CORD architecture, the virtualization component will enable multi-tenancy and dynamic provision of location, capacity and latency information. This will allow optimally mapping of services to the available resources. Standardized interfaces shall provide simple integration of stationary and mobile user equipment. As the default CORD setup consists of multiple devices (e.g., switches, servers, UPSs etc.) distributed in several racks, the portability factor is minimum. A portable alternative, could be represented by a Cord-In-A-Box deployment which would concentrate a minimum CORD testing functionality inside a powerful off-the-shelf server.

3. Performance metrics of the Selected Vertical Use Cases

This chapter focuses on the three vertical use cases that have been selected among those presented in the previous chapter and derived from WP2 activities (see project deliverable D2.1). These vertical use cases, further details in the following three subsections, will be implemented and validated within Metro-Haul. For each selected vertical use case, the relevant performance metrics and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be demonstrated will be highlighted. Such analysis and KPIs will form the basis for the feedback to WP3, WP4 and other WP5 tasks in their design and deployment criteria.

3.2 Crowdsourced video broadcasts

In this subsection, we further detail the use case described in Section 2.9, which was identified as the first relevant vertical use case to be demonstrated within the Metro-Haul project.

3.2.3 Specific aspects to be demonstrated targeting KPIs

To satisfy application connectivity requirements Metro-Haul nodes need to do the following:

At the AMEN/Metro network it will be necessary to have:

- Computing capability at AMEN to process video and sensor data to aggregate and form clusters of crowd videos
- Dynamic high capacity paths to upload clustered video streams. Data rates of ~10Gbps for a 30K capacity stadium
- Monitor and gather video application requirements and provide network services.
- Provide virtual load layer4/7 load balancers, content caching, compression and TCP/IP multiplexing

At the MCEN/Core network it will be necessary to have:

- Processing power to identify individual video clusters to provide paths to different datacentre facilities
- Multiple routes (upload/download multi-path TCP) to reach video application data centre
- Monitor and gather video application requirements and provide network services. E.g. Jitter, bandwidth, as the number of video clusters allocate more paths to different cloud locations
- Provide load balancing, between multiple data centre routes, to manage scale

3.2.4 KPIs to be demonstrated

- MH1 100 x more 5G capacity supported over the same optical fibre infrastructure (edge processing)
- MH3 Latency-aware metro network in which latency-sensitive slices are handled at the metro edge ensuring the metro network adds no additional latency.
- MH4 End to end SDN-based management framework enabling fast configuration time to set up or reconfigure services handling 5G applications, specifically 1 minute for simple network path set-up and 10 minutes for full installation of a new VNF and 1 hour for setting up a new virtual network

KPIs to be demonstrated	Target value
MH1 : High edge bandwidth required to scale video uploads	Multiples of 10G
MH3: Low jitter and latency for video streams	Milliseconds range
MH3: Time to spawn computing resources	Few seconds

MH3: Time to increase/decrease the capacity of video streams	Few seconds (excluding network device configuration)
MH4: SDN-based management framework enabling fast configuration time to set up or reconfigure services handling 5G applications	Few seconds (excluding network device configuration)
Interface IO-4 for other modules to get monitoring data from applications, networking and computing resources.	Available
Interface IO-3 for applications to request VNF reconfiguration for load balancing	Available

3.2.5 Scheduling

The high level scheduling is shown in Figure 17 (detailed scheduling will be described in the future project Deliverable D5.2)

Figure 17 – High level scheduling of the Crowdsourced video broadcasts Demo

3.2.6 Feedback/requirements to WP3 and WP4

For the detailed design and description of the demonstrator, which is planned in task T5.2, input from WP3 and WP4 is required. In particular WP4 activities are the focal point. It is important that details on the planned functionality of the internal software releases MS16 M3.3, MS17 M4.3, MS21 M3.5, and MS22 M4.4 are communicated as early as possible.

3.3 Real-time low-latency object tracking

In this subsection, we further detail the use case described in Ch.2.10, which has been identified as the second relevant vertical use case to be demonstrated within the Metro-Haul project.

3.3.3 Specific aspects to be demonstrated targeting KPIs

Figure 18 – Video security use case overview and relevant network sections in Metro-Haul.

The video security use case is built upon the real-time availability of results derived from the processing of video data, which is captured from various camera sources. In general, the cameras can be fixed cameras or mobile cameras such as e.g. cameras mounted on drones, body cams or tablet/smartphone cams. Security is then provided by automatic detection and tracking of suspects who are stored in databases. This enables security forces e.g. at airports or train stations to immediately act when suspects enter the premises. In principle, the system can also be used to track number plates of cars, e.g. in the event of car theft.

In order to enable real-time availability of processing results and thus time-critical interactions and intervention on critical events the processing of video data should be performed as close to the camera sources as possible [6]. In particular, latency due to optical transport of the video streams through the metro domain⁴ may not be tolerable for time-critical applications. Furthermore, for dense deployments of high-resolution cameras (e.g. 4k), it may be undesirable to provision bandwidth for these video streams in the metro network. Pre-processing at the edge, which extracts the relevant features from the video streams, significantly reduces traffic load in the metro domain.

Another important aspect is the geographical distribution of the cameras. Owners of camera networks (such as e.g. public authorities) may operate cameras, which are distributed over a wide area (e.g. a city). For many applications, value is created by merging the information of all or some of the distributed cameras and making it available at a desired location in the network. By virtualizing the physical resources responsible for compute, storage and networking, such regionally distributed camera networks can be operated efficiently with dynamically assigned resources.

The key aspects that are targeted for demonstration are thus:

- 1) Low-latency edge processing of video data
- 2) Instantiation of a virtual private network incorporating distributed camera deployment, networking, compute and storage resources.

3.3.4 KPIs to be demonstrated

It is planned to evaluate the key KPIs identified in Milestone *MS3 M2.1 “Collection of selected proposals on Use Cases and Services”* and deliverable *D2.1 “Definition of use cases, Service*

⁴ A distance of 100 km causes a roundtrip delay of ~1ms due to speed of light alone

Requirements and KPIs”, the main KPI being latency. The demonstrated key aspects as described in the previous section directly relate to the following Metro-Haul KPIs.

- MH1 100 x more 5G capacity supported over the same optical fibre infrastructure (edge processing)
- MH3 Latency-aware metro network in which latency-sensitive slices are handled at the metro edge ensuring the metro network adds no additional latency.
- MH4 End to end SDN-based management framework enabling fast configuration time to set up or reconfigure services handling 5G applications, specifically 1 minute for simple network path set-up and 10 minutes for full installation of a new VNF and 1 hour for setting up a new virtual network

3.3.5 Scheduling

The high level scheduling is shown in Figure 19 (detailed scheduling will be described in the future project Deliverable D5.2)

Figure 19 – High-level scheduling for the demonstrator of the real-time low-latency object tracking and security Demo.

3.3.6 Feedback/requirements to WP3 and WP4

For the detailed design and description of the demonstrator, which is planned in Task 5.2, input from WP3 and WP4 is required. In particular, it is important that details on the planned functionality of the internal software releases MS16 M3.3, MS17 M4.3, MS21 M3.5, and MS22 M4.4 are communicated as early as possible. Similarly, information on available OIEs planned for MS20 M3.4 and MS24 M3.6 is invaluable for the upcoming demonstrator design.

3.4 Portable Demo on Media and Entertainment

In this subsection, we further detail a use case on content delivery network which has been identified as the third relevant vertical use case to be demonstrated within the Metro-Haul project. This vertical use case has been selected since it encompasses requirements, technologies, and solutions that are common for multiple use cases analysed in project deliverable D2.1. More specifically, it addresses the software components in scope of Metro-Haul of the CDN use case, the Live TV use case, and the

6DoF use case. Moreover, it is suitable for integration and experimentation of the passive and active network measurement probes.

3.4.3 Specific aspects to be demonstrated targeting KPIs

To illustrate how the Metro-Haul COM architecture can support applications based on VNFFGs, in this section we propose a Content Delivery Network (CDN) manager to adapt the virtualized CDN function for live-TV and video on demand (VoD) distribution that collects monitoring data from the caches and dynamically reconfigures them to current and future demand. By virtualizing the CDN function, CDN costs can be minimized by dynamically adapting computing and network resources to current and future users' needs while ensuring the highest quality [7].

The MPEG Dynamic Adaptive Streaming (MPEG-DASH) technique [8] is used to mitigate disruptions in the video distribution service during the reconfigurations. MPEG-DASH enables media content delivering over HTTP protocol using standard HTTP web servers' infrastructures to users' devices. In that regard, MPEG-DASH divides contents into a sequence of small file segments, each containing a short interval, e.g., 2 seconds, of the content and provides mechanisms to request the segmented contents.

A virtualized hierarchical CDN can be deployed on the Metro-Haul infrastructure with some few primary caches that are the entrance point for new multimedia contents and a number of Leaf Cache Nodes running in COs, close to end users: a centralized CDN Admission and Control module implements CDN user access policies and redirects users' requests, e.g., based on their geographical location, to the leaf cache node that will serve them. Leaf cache nodes distribute VoD and live-TV: VoD contents are stored in leaf caches based on its popularity [9] and live-TV content is locally prepared in leaf cache nodes [10].

A virtualized leaf cache node would consist of the following components running as software inside VMs deployed in the same CO. The packager is in charge of live-TV preparation, including segmentation and MPD generation. The HTTP server component serves end users' segment requests. The Cache Manager is the entry point of the cache node; it receives users' requests, identifies which contents will be locally stored, and redirects users' requests to the appropriate HTTP server. Each component usually consists in a pool of resources for load balancing and redundancy purposes. The amount of resources in every resource pool can be dynamically adapted in response to spikes in demand, e.g. a sports event.

Finally, a CDN Manager is responsible for adapting the CDN to the current and future load. To that end, monitoring data is collected from the MDA controller and analysed; specifically, the logs from the cache manager that contain useful information regarding user activity and contents access together with the activity of the packagers and HTTP servers are analysed. The analysed performance and load of the CDN is used to elastically adapt its resources to current and near future service needs.

A configuration manager is in charge of interfacing the NFVO to request and release IT and networking resources and of properly configuring every component. Figure 20 presents the proposed architecture and the control loops that allow to dynamically adapt the CDN. Specifically, in this paper we focus on demonstrating two workflows: WF1 is related to the CDN self-adaptation by scaling up/down in the event of an increment/decrement in the amount of contents being served from a given leaf cache node, whereas WF2 focuses on pushing new contents from the primary cache toward the leaf cache nodes and it is supported by the dynamic set-up of optical connections. Figure 21 details the proposed workflows.

Figure 20 – Autonomous network service management use case.

WF1 starts when new monitoring data is collected by the MDA agents. In particular, a set of observation points (OP) are defined for the CDN from which measurements are performed, including the logs from the cache managers, HTTP servers, and packagers, status of computing (e.g. CPU load, memory, etc.), storage resources (e.g. capacity used, number of files, etc.), and networking (e.g., throughput and latency). In the workflow, measurements are collected from the local cache manager and the VIM in a CO from (messages 1 and 2 of WF1 in Figure 21). The MDA agent can aggregate monitoring data to adapt the monitoring period to the one required by the MDA controller, aiming to control the amount of monitoring data that is conveyed [11]. MDA agents send aggregated monitoring data to the MDA controller (3), which becomes accessible for the applications. Periodically, the CDN manager interrogates the MDA controller regarding monitoring data availability for the defined OPs, and monitoring data is retrieved from the MDA monitoring data repository and sent toward the CDN manager.

Collected monitoring data is analysed by the CDN manager. Precisely, the Data Processor module is the placeholder for machine learning algorithms able to discover knowledge from data. For instance, in the case that the resources allocated in a leaf cache node become not enough in the near future to satisfy the required QoE of the users being served by a leaf cache node, the CDN controller might reconfigure such leaf cache in advance [7]. Hence, the CDN controller request the NFVO to scale the VNF by increasing the number of HTTP servers and incrementing the capacity of the packet network

toward the users (6-13). Finally, the availability of a new HTTP server is announced to the local cache manager, so it can add that server to the local pool.

Figure 21 – CDN-driven workflows supported by the Metro-Haul COM system.

WF2 starts when new content is available in the primary caches (message 0 of WF2 in Figure 21) and the CDN manager decides to make it available for the users. In such case, the CDN manager issues a request to the NFVO to extend the current forwarding graph to connect a primary cache (PC) with a set of leaf caches (LC), specifying the required capacity to be supported (1). The NFVO translates the request into a request to set-up a multicast connection to the WIM (2), and depending on the capacity requirements, the connection is set-up at the optical layer or at the MPLS layer [12]. In the case of a high-capacity connection, the WIM decides to establish a light-tree (3-4) and extends the connectivity in the CO at the packet layer (5-6). When the connectivity is ready, the NFVO extends the VLAN associated to the VNFFG (9) and announces the cache manager that new content is available (10).

3.4.4 KPIs to be demonstrated

The KPIs to be demonstrated in WP5 are related to the general KPI **MH4 – End to end SDN-based management framework enabling fast configuration time to set up or reconfigure services handling 5G applications**, as well as with the requirements for the live-TV use case described in Deliverable D2.1. The specific KPIs are described in the next table:

KPIs to be demonstrated	Target value
Time to scale up a leaf cache in terms of computing resources	few seconds (plus VM start-up)
Time to increase/decrease the capacity of LSPs for a leaf cache to serve the users	few seconds (excluding network device configuration)
Time to establish a connection from the primary cache to a leaf cache for content synchronization	few seconds (excluding network device configuration)

Interface IO-4 for other modules (COM or applications) to get monitoring data from applications, networking and computing resources.	Available
Interface M-COM for the MDA system to synchronize operational data bases from COM modules (SDN and Data Centre controllers and NFVO)	Available
Interface IO-3 for applications to request VNF reconfiguration	Available

3.4.5 Scheduling

The high level plan (detailed plans will be described in the future project deliverable D5.2) is as follows:

- Implementation of monitoring interfaces for applications, data centres and network devices.
- Implementation of IO-4 and MCOM
- Implementation of IO-3
- Adaptation of existing CDN software to the Metro-Haul architecture
- Availability of an initial proof-of-concept (Q3)
- Availability of the demonstrator v1 (Q8)
- Availability of the demonstrator v2 (Q11)

3.4.6 Feedback/requirements to WP3 and WP4

It is required input from WP3 and especially from WP4 regarding the functionality planned for the demonstrator.

4. Conclusions

This project deliverable D5.1 has discussed the feasibility of implementing three specific Metro-Haul demonstrations to showcase the capabilities and benefits of the Metro-Haul architecture in supporting the following service use cases as previously analysed in WP2 and reported in the project deliverable D2.1:

- a) mIoT Utility metering
- b) Capacity planning of Content Delivery Network
- c) Live TV distribution
- d) Service Robotics
- e) Smart Factory
- f) 6DoF Virtual Reality
- g) Intelligent environments to support Autonomous Driving
- h) Enterprise Access with NG Ethernet
- i) Crowdsourced video broadcasts
- j) Real-time low-latency object tracking

In this deliverable, each use case has been briefly discussed and further analysed in terms of the feasibility of experimental validation, the innovation to be demonstrated, and its portability. As an outcome of the analysis, the following three demos were confirmed for validation in WP5:

1. Crowdsourced video broadcasts
2. Real-time low-latency object tracking
3. Portable Demo on Media and Entertainment

The first two demos were already pre-selected in the Metro-Haul project proposal phase, and will target the validation of the following Metro-Haul KPIs:

- MH1: 100 x more 5G capacity supported over the same optical fibre infrastructure (edge processing).
- MH3: Latency-aware metro network in which latency-sensitive slices are handled at the metro edge ensuring the metro network adds no additional latency.
- MH4: End-to-end SDN-based management framework enabling fast configuration time to set up or reconfigure services handling 5G applications, specifically 1 minute for simple network path set-up, 10 minutes for full installation of a new VNF, and 1 hour for setting up a new virtual network.

The third demo on media and entertainment was then also selected for validation in WP5 since it represents a multiple number of the use cases analysed in WP2. In particular, the third demo has been chosen to demonstrate the software components in support of the CDN use case, the Live-TV use case, and the 6DoF use case. Moreover, it also includes the experimentation of the passive and active network measurement probes identified within the Enterprise Access with NG Ethernet use case. This third demo will further address the KPI MH4, focusing on a set of more specific KPIs, as detailed in this document.

The other two Metro-Haul KPIs (MH2 & H5) are more appropriate to being assessed and validated in the parallel work packages WP3 and WP2, respectively.

This document also provides feedback into the project as a whole on the specific technical requirements and solutions to be addressed for the validation of the considered objectives and demonstration sessions.

5. List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
3DoF	Three(3) Degrees of Freedom
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
5G PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6DoF	Six(6) Degrees of Freedom
ABNO	Application Based Network Operations
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AMEN	Access Metro Edge Node
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
BBU	Base Band Unit
BER	Bit Error Rate
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CCTV	Closed Circuit Television
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CN	Core Network
CORD	Central Office Re-architected as a Datacentre
CoS	Class of Service
CoS	Class of Service
CPRI	Common Public Radio Interface
CPS	Cyber Physical System
CriC	Critical Connections
CU	Centralized Unit
DA	Data Analytics
DASH	Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP
DB	Data Base
DC	Data Centre
DM	Data Mining
DU	Distributed Unit
EB	Exabyte
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broad Band
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
GMPLS	Generalized Multi-Protocol Label Switching
GPON	Gigabit Passive Optical Network
GPU	Graphic Processing Unit
GSMA	Global Mobile Supplier Association (Industrial Association)
HD	High Definition

HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
IaaS	Infrastructure-as-a-Service
IoE	Internet of Everything
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technologies
ITS	Intelligent Transportation System
KB	Kilobyte
KDD	Knowledge Discovery on Database
KPI	Key Performance Index
MB	Megabyte
MCEN	Metro Core Edge Node
mIoT	Massive Internet of Things
MPD	Media Presentation Description
MPEG	Moving Picture Experts Group
MR	Mixed Reality
NBI	North-Bound Interface
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NFV-I	Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure
NFV-O	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
NGMN	Next Generation Mobile Networks (Industrial Association)
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturers
OLT	Optical Line Terminal
OSS	Operations Support System
PaaS	Platform-as-a-Service
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PTZ	Pan Tilt Zoom
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
QoE	Quality of Experience
RN	Radio Network
RU	Radio Unit
SaaS	Software-as-a-Service
SD	Standard Definition
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
T-SDN	Transport-SDN
UHD	Ultra-High Definition
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Connections
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2N	Vehicle to Network (Internet servers)
V2P	Vehicle to Pedestrian
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle

V2X	Vehicle to Everything
VR	Virtual Reality
WAN	Wide Area Network
XR	Extended Reality
ZB	Zetabyte
FLOPS	FLoating point Operations Per Second

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